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Original Article

Eosinophils and T cell surface molecule transcript levels in the blood differentiate eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) from GERD

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Abstract

We recently rereported that blood mRNA levels of T cells and IgE receptors are the novel non-invasive biomarkers for eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) with the aim to establish the panel of T cells and IgE receptor as the novel non-invasive biomarkers for EoE. In addition to earlier proposed cell surface molecules, we now add T cell receptor CXCR6 and eosinophils expressed cell surface molecules CD101 and CD274 mRNA levels. The mRNA levels of eosinophils cell surface molecule CD101 and CD274 and T cell receptor CXCR6, V β 11, CD1d and chemokine CXCL16 levels were examined using the blood of normal, EoE and GERD patients. The analysis showed statistically significant induced mRNA levels of CD274, CD101 and reduced CXCR6 will be an additional molecule with respective 95%, 90% and 90% positive predictive value in between EoE and GERD patients. In brief, these additional data will be critical to establish a complete panel of earlier published TCR δ (95%), J α 18 (83%) and FC ϵ R2 (100%) non-invasive biomarker to monitor the EoE severity and treatment effect in EoE patients. In conclusion, we now propose both induced and reduced transcript levels of cell surface molecules of the cell surface molecules along with earlier reported molecules that will be useful for monitoring EoE status before and following treatment. Most importantly, the complete predictive non-invasive biomarker panel will also serve to differentiate EoE from GERD.

Keywords: Biomarker, Eosinophils, CD101, CD274, CXCR6

Introduction

Expert panel consensus recommendations (FIGURE2) of an interdisciplinary expert physicians define that eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) represents a chronic, immune/antigen-mediated esophageal disease characterized clinically by symptoms related to esophageal dysfunction and histologically by eosinophil predominant inflammation.¹ Further, regarding

diagnostic the recommendation suggested that the patients biopsy specimens must show eosinophil-predominant inflammation with 15 eosinophils/hpf (peak value) as minimum threshold for a diagnosis of EoE.² Another diagnostic consensus recommendation was published in AGRE conference 2018 that indicated esophageal biopsy remains the only reliable diagnostic test for EoE; however, the panel did not recommend

molecules in invasive study of a panel of serum biomarkers found that none of the markers studied correlate with disease.³⁻⁶ A novel non-invasive biomarker is lacking that differentiate EoE from other esophageal disorders like closely related gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). We earlier reported that in the esophageal biopsies of EoE patients IL-15 and iNKT cells are induced⁷⁻⁹ and most recently evaluated the levels of mRNA expression of several potential molecules related IL-15 and its responsive iNKT cell surface molecules and receptors in the blood of EoE patients and showed by ROC curve analysis that TCR δ (95%), J α 18 (83%) and FC ϵ RII (100%) have positive predictive value in support of individual novel marker for EoE that differentiate clearly EoE from GERD.¹⁰ Since we earlier reported that human blood has both CD274 expressing (CD274⁺) and not expressing (CD274⁻) eosinophils in normal individuals and EoE patients.³ Therefore, we further examined blood mRNA levels of CD274 and CD101 with some other critical T cells receptors and associated chemokines based on our earlier preliminary report that indicated induced CD274-expressing eosinophils and CD274 mRNA levels in one pediatric and one adult EoE patients compare to normal and their levels reduces following the treatment.¹¹ We extended these observation and now present that indeed the mRNA levels of eosinophils cell surface molecules CD274, CD101 is significantly induced along with significantly reduced T cell receptor CXCR6 in EoE patients compare to the normal individuals and GERD patients. The ROC curve analysis showed CD274, CD101 and CXCR6 transcript has 95%, 90%, and 90% positive predictive value, respectively. Thus, with the inclusion of these additional data, we now predict that the panel of blood mRNA levels of CD274, CD101, CXCR6, TCR δ , J α 18, and FC ϵ RII as the novel non-invasive biomarkers for EoE that even differentiate EoE from GERD patients.

Materials and Methods

1. Details of Patients characteristics. The normal individuals, GERD and EoE patients were selected without regard to age, atopic status, or gender. The treatment strategies for EoE including dietary restriction of food allergens or topical fluticasone therapy and for GERD including PPI therapy are listed in **Table 1**, as described in published in our recently.¹⁰

2. Patient Blood Collection and Blood RNA Isolation. human *GAPDH* amplified from the same cDNA mix and expressed as relative gene expression. cDNA was amplified using the primers listed in **Table 2**.

3. Measurement of Biomarkers mRNA Levels by

RT-PCR Analysis. Quantitative PCR analysis was performed on blood RNA (500 ng) and it was subjected to reverse transcription analysis using iScript reverse transcriptase (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. *CD274*, *CD101*, *T cell receptor-CXCR6*, *Chemokine ligand 16 (CXCL16)*, iNKT cell receptor (*V β 11*) and activated iNKT cell receptor (*CD1d*) were quantified by real-time PCR using IQ5 (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA). Results were then normalized to human *GAPDH* amplified from the same cDNA mix and expressed as relative gene expression. cDNA was amplified using the primers listed in **Table 2**.

4. Statistical Analysis. Esophageal eosinophil counts from each patient were calculated by averaging the mean eosinophil counts obtained from the proximal and distal esophagus. All statistical tests were compared using *t* tests or analysis of variance. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). *p* values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant. Statistical tests were performed using GraphPad Prism 5 Software (San Diego, CA).

Results

Induced mRNA levels of naïve and pathogenic eosinophils cell surface molecules CD101 and CD274 in EoE, GERD patients and normal individuals.

Most recently, we and others reported a distinguishable subset of CD101¹² and CD274¹³ expressing eosinophils, similar to the other immune cell subset

Figure 1. Analysis of mRNA levels of naïve and pathogenic eosinophils cell surface molecules CD274 and CD101. RT-PCR analysis of naïve and pathogenic eosinophil differentiation cell surface molecules CD274 (A) and CD101 (B) in EoE, GERD patients and normal individuals. Each data points indicate individual transcripts expression levels in patients. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis of CD274 and CD101 discriminate between patients with EoE compared to GERD (C, D). The solid line (r discrimination) indicates values that have no discriminatory value. Note that on the vertical axis, the scale is from no (0%) to complete (100%) sensitivity. The horizontal axis is reciprocal scale (100% - % specificity). The optimum performance of a diagnostic test determined either at the highest sum of the sensitivity and specificity or at an acceptable level of sensitivity for the given disease. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, n=3; EoE: 3 patients, GERD: 19 patients, normal individual: 15 nos. Some patient data points are missing as they did not show up during PCR analysis. EoE vs Normal *** $p < 0.0003$, ** $p < 0.01$; EoE vs GERD ## $p < 0.01$.

populations that exhibit differences in their phenotypes and functions. Earlier, we reported possibility of induced CD101 and CD274 expressing eosinophils may be used to diagnose eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) in patients,^{11,13} and now in this report we validated this possibility by analyzing large number of patient's blood and confirm that indeed the number of CD274 expressing eosinophils increases with disease severity and decreases following the treatment.¹¹ We examined blood mRNA levels of eosinophils cell surface molecule CD274 and CD101 expression in normal, EoE and GERD patients. We present the data that show significantly induced CD274 and CD101 mRNA levels in the blood of EoE patients compared to GERD patients and non-EoE individuals (Fig 1 A-B). The specificity and sensitivity of these two eosinophils cell surface molecules CD101 and CD274 were compared between normal, EoE and GERD patients. The cut-off levels were determined by ROC curve analysis to maximize the sensitivity and specificity of CD101 and CD274 biomarkers that differentiate EoE from normal and GERD as described earlier.¹⁰ The ROC curve analysis of CD274 (95%) and CD101 (90%) in individual yielded an excellent positive predictive value for EoE patient that even differentiate clearly EoE from GERD (Fig 1 C-D). These results further establish that the induced blood mRNA levels CD274 and CD101 will be a novel biomarker that differentiate EoE from GERD.

Relative expression analysis of CXCR6 in EoE patients compared to normal individuals and GERD patients.

The CXCR6 receptor is also expressed by T cell subset including iNKT cells; therefore, we also examined CXCR6 mRNA expression in the blood of normal individual, EoE, and GERD patients. Similar to the other reported iNKT cells specific mRNA levels, we also observed significantly reduced CXCR6 mRNA in EoE patients compared to normal and GERD patients. (Fig 2, A) with the 90% specificity and sensitivity by ROC curve analysis that yielded an excellent positive predictive value in support of individual marker for EoE patient that differentiate clearly EoE from GERD (Fig 2 B).

Relative expression of non-specific iNKT cell receptors ($V\beta 11$, CD1d) and chemokine (CXCL16) mRNA levels in the blood of normal, EoE, and GERD patients.

Most recently, we reported that IL-15-responsive iNKT cells, iNKT cell receptor ($V\alpha 24$, $J\alpha 18$) are

Figure 2. Analysis of CXCR6 in EoE patients compared to normal individuals and GERD patients. RT-PCR analysis of CXCR6 mRNA expression levels in the blood samples of the EoE patients, GERD, and normal individuals. Each data points indicate individual transcripts expression levels in patients (A). Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis of CXCR6 to discriminate between patients with EoE compared to GERD (B). The solid line (no discrimination) indicates values that have no discriminatory value. Note that on the vertical axis, the scale is from no (0%) to complete (100%) sensitivity. The horizontal axis is a reciprocal scale (100% - % specificity). The optimum performance of a diagnostic test is determined either at the highest sum of the sensitivity and specificity or at an acceptable level of sensitivity for the given disease. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, n=3; EoE: 33 patients, GERD: 19 patients, normal individual: 15 nos. Some patient data points are missing as they did not show up during PCR analysis. EoE vs Normal *** p<0.0003; EoE vs GERD ### p<0.001.

highly expressed in the esophagus, and their levels are reduced in the blood of patients with EoE compared with GERD patients and non-EoE individuals.^{9,10} Therefore, we further examined few other receptors and chemokines that are present and are shown to be involved in the homing of iNKT and other T cells subsets.⁹ The receptor $V\beta 11$ and CD1d mRNA level is found decreased in EoE patients compare to normal individuals; but no difference between GERD patients and non-EoE individuals (Fig 3A, C). The specificity and sensitivity of $V\beta 11$ and CD1d were compared between EoE and GERD patients. The ROC curve analysis for specificity and sensitivity of $V\beta 11$ and CD1d yielded not much positive predictive value (67% and 92%,) respectively; but between normal individual to EoE patients yielded only 57% (Fig 3 B, D). Thus, both $V\beta 11$ and CD1d cannot be a used

Figure 2. Analysis of CXCR6 in EoE patients compared to normal individuals and GERD patients. RT-PCR analysis of CXCR6 mRNA expression levels in the blood samples of the EoE patients, GERD, and normal individuals. Each data points indicate individual transcripts expression levels in patients (A). Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis of CXCR6 to discriminate between patients with EoE compared to GERD (B). The solid line (no discrimination) indicates values that have no discriminatory value. Note that on the vertical axis, the scale is from no (0%) to complete (100%) sensitivity. The horizontal axis is a reciprocal scale (100% - % specificity). The optimum performance of a diagnostic test is determined either at the highest sum of the sensitivity and specificity or at an acceptable level of sensitivity for the given disease. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, n=3; EoE: 33 patients, GERD: 19 patients, normal individual: 15 nos. Some patient data points are missing as they did not show up during PCR analysis. EoE vs Normal *** p<0.0003; EoE vs GERD ### p<0.001.

Table 1: Patients Clinical and pathological characteristics

Abbreviations:

Patients	Age	Gender	Esophageal disease	Allergic diseases	Current Treatment
1	9	M	NL	Asthma	None
2	11	F	NL	Unknown	None
3	7	F	NL	None	H1RA
4	9	F	NL	Unknown	INHGC,LTRA
5	4	M	NL	Rhinitis	LTRA
6	12	M	NL	None	INHGC
7	5	F	NL	Unknown	INHGC
8	11	M	NL	None	PPI, OGC
9	9	M	NL	Asthma	None
10	10	M	NL	None	INHGC, SWGC
11	12	M	NL	None	None
12	13	F	NL	Unknown	PPI
13	10	M	NL	Asthma	INHGC
14	12	M	NL	None	PPI
15	14	F	EoE	Asthma	INHGC
16	4	M	EoE	None	INHGC
17	9	F	EoE	Rhinitis/Asthma/Food allergy	PPI, mesalamine
18	8	M	EoE	Food Allergy	Alimentary diet
19	10	M	EoE	None	None
20	8	F	EoE	Asthma/Eczema	Alimentary diet, INHGC
21	9	F	EoE	Rhinitis/Asthma	Alimentary diet, INHGC
22	6	M	EoE	Unknown	INHGC,B2ARA
23	11	F	EoE	Food Allergy	None
24	4	F	EoE	Asthma	Alimentary diet, INHGC
25	5	M	EoE	None	INHGC
26	10	F	EoE	Asthma/Eczema	None
27	6	M	EoE	None	PPI
28	7	M	EoE	Rhinitis/Asthma	B2ARA
29	15	F	EoE	Food Allergy/anaphylaxis	Alimentary diet, Protonix
30	8	M	EoE	None	Alimentary diet, PPI
31	11	M	EoE	Asthma/Rhinitis	Alimentary diet
32	21	F	EoE	Rhinitis/eczema	Alimentary diet, SWGC
33	9	M	EoE	Unknown	B2ARA
34	13	M	EoE	Food Allergy	SWGC,PPI
35	18	F	EoE	Asthma/Rhinitis	SWGC, H1RA
36	8	M	EoE	Eczema	Alimentary diet, SWGC
37	11	M	EoE	Unknown	PPI
38	20	M	EoE	Rhinitis	Alimentary diet, PPI
39	8	M	EoE	Unknown	Alimentary diet, INHGC
40	20	F	EoE	Asthma	PPI
41	11	M	EoE	None	None
42	7	M	EoE	Asthma/Eczema	INHGC
43	11	F	EoE	Rhinitis	INHGC,PPI
44	12	M	EoE	None	B2ARA
45	8	F	EoE	Food Allergy/anaphylaxis/Asthma	SWGC, Alimentary diet
46	11	M	EoE	Unknown	PPI
47	20	M	GERD	Rhinitis	Alimentary diet,
48	18	M	GERD	Unknown	Alimentary diet, INHGC
49	20	F	GERD	Asthma	PPI
50	11	M	GERD	None	None
51	7	M	GERD	Asthma/Eczema	INHGC
52	11	F	GERD	Rhinitis	INHGC,PPI
53	12	M	GERD	None	B2ARA
54	8	F	GERD	Food Allergy/anaphylaxis/Asthma	SWGC, Alimentary diet
55	13	M	GERD	Asthma	OGC
56	18	F	GERD	Unknown	None
57	8	M	GERD	None	H1RA
58	11	M	GERD	Unknown	INHGC,LTRA
59	20	M	GERD	Rhinitis	LTRA,
60	8	M	GERD	None	INHGC, INHGC
61	20	F	GERD	Asthma/ Food allergy	INHGC
62	4	F	GERD	None	PPI
63	5	M	GERD	Rhinitis/eczema	Alimentary diet, SWGC
64	10	F	GERD	Unknown	B2ARA
65	6	M	GERD	Food Allergy	SWGC,PPI

NL=normal, M=male, F= female, EoE= eosinophilic esophagitis, GERD. LTRA, leukotriene receptor antagonist; H1RA, H1-receptor antagonist; INHGC, inhaled glucocorticoid; B2ARA, 2 adrenergic receptor antagonists; PPI, proton pump inhibitor; SWGC, swallowed glucocorticoid (fluticasone); OGC, oral glucocorticoid (prednisone).

as a reliable biomarker for EoE. Additionally, we also examined mRNA levels *CXCL16*, that also found reduced in EoE vs GERD patients, but no significant change compared to the normal individuals (**Fig 3E**). The ROC curve analysis for specificity and sensitivity of *CXCL16* between EoE and GERD yielded (98%), but yielded only 47% between normal individual to EoE patients (**Fig 3F**). Notably, all these receptor *Vβ11*, *CD1d* and chemokine *CXCL16* are not specific to iNKT cells and found in several other T cell subsets and antigen presenting cells.¹⁴⁻¹⁷

Figure 3. Relative expression of non-specific iNKT cell receptors (*Vβ11*, *CD1d*) and chemokine (*CXCL16*) mRNA levels in the blood of normal, EoE, and GERD patients. RT-PCR analysis of T cell receptors mRNA levels of *Vβ11* (A), *CD1d* (C) and their chemokine *CXCL16* (E) in EoE, GERD and normal individuals are shown. Each data points indicate individual transcripts expression levels of each patient. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis for sensitivity and specificity of these T cell receptors between patients with EoE compared to normal individuals are analyzed (B, D and F). The solid line (no discrimination) indicates values that have no discriminatory value. Note that on the vertical axis, the scale is from no (0%) to complete (100%) sensitivity. The horizontal axis is a reciprocal scale (100% - % specificity). The optimum performance of a diagnostic test is determined either at the highest sum of the sensitivity and specificity or at an acceptable level of sensitivity for the given disease. Data are expressed as mean± SD, n=3; EoE: 33 patients, GERD: 19 patients, normal individual: 15 nos. Some patient data points are missing as they did not show up during PCR analysis. EoE vs Normal ** p<0.01, * p<0.05; EoE vs GERD, #p<0.05, ## p<0.01, NS, not significant.

Summarized ROC curve positive predictive value for the non-invasive biomarker's specificity for EoE. Herein, we present a combined panel of earlier reported genes¹⁰ and present additional mRNA levels of eosinophils and T cell surface molecule *CD274*, *CD101* and *CXCR6* mRNA level with the percent of positive predictive values compare to the GERD patients.

Table 2: List of human primer sequences

Genes	Sense and anti-sense primer sequence (5'-3')
<i>h-Vβ11</i>	F: 5'- TCAACAGTCTCCAGAATAAGGACG -3'
	R: 5'- GTGGGAGATCTCTGCTTCTG -3'
<i>h-CD1d</i>	F: 5'- GCCTGTCTGTCTGGGTGAA -3'
	R: 5'- GCTGTTCTCTCCTCATTGTGGG -3'
<i>h-CXCR6</i>	F: 5'- ATGCCATGACCAGCTTTTCACT -3'
	R: 5'-TTAAGGCAGGCCCTCAGG -3'
<i>h-CXCL16</i>	F: 5'- GGCCCACCAGAAGCATTTCAC -3'
	R: 5'- CTGAAGATGCCCCCTCTGAG -3'
<i>h-CD274</i>	F: 5'- CATTGCTGAACGCCCCATA -3'
	R: 5'- TCTTGAATTGGTGGTGGTG -3'
<i>h-CD101</i>	F: 5'- TCGTTCCTCCTCTGCTCGTT -3'
	R: 5'- GCCGGATGGCCTTGTACTTT -3'
<i>h-GAPDH</i>	F: 5'- TGGAAATCCCATCACCAT -3'
	R: 5'- GTCTTCTGGGTGGCAGTGA -3'

Table 3. The complete panel ROC curve of biomarker

Name of GENES	Levels in blood of human EOE compared to Normal and GERD	Percent ROC Curve positive predictive value (EoE vs GERD)
CD274	Induced	95
CD101	Induced	90
FcεRII	Reduced	100
TCRδ	Reduced	95
Ja18α	Reduced	83
Vβ11	Reduced	67
CXCR6	Reduced	90

The complete panel ROC curve of biomarkers is presented in table 3.

Discussion

CD274 is recognized as an activation and maturation marker of T cells¹⁸ and we showed CD274 expression on the eosinophils present in allergic patients EoE.^{3,13} We earlier showed that CD274-expressing blood eosinophils in both pediatric and adult EoE patients that suggested CD274⁺ eosinophils or their mRNA levels may be a possible blood biomarker for human EoE. The two EoE patient reported blood eosinophil analysis showed a strong relation between CD274 expression on eosinophils and histological esophageal biopsy

findings. However, in the earlier report we did not compare the CD274 expression levels on the Examined eosinophils of GERD patients. We now large number of normal, EoE and GERD patients and observed a significantly induced levels of CD274, CD101 and CXCR6 mRNA levels in EoE patients compare to the normal individuals and GERD patients with the 95%, 90%, 90% positive predictive value by ROC curve analysis, respectively in between EoE and GERD patients. Additionally, we also observed few additional T cell receptor mRNA levels like CXCR6 and V β 11 mRNA levels that also differentiate EoE from GERD. Blood tests are not used for EoE diagnosis; but our constant approach now indicate that blood test is useful for the diagnosis of EoE and GERD patients. The presented blood mRNA analysis for T cell receptor-CXCR6, iNKT cell receptor (V β 11), eosinophils express CD274 and CD101 cell surface molecules along with earlier reported blood mRNA levels of T cells and IgE receptors are the novel non-invasive biomarkers for EoE. Additionally, we also recommend initially the expression of CD274 on the blood eosinophils may also be used to differentiate EoE from GERD. Thus, the presented data suggest that peripheral blood mRNA levels of reported molecules are the relevant biomarker panel for monitoring disease activity in EoE patients. In conclusion, we now propose mRNA levels of CD274, CD101, CXCR6, TCR δ , Ja18, and FC ϵ RII are the novel non-invasive biomarkers panel for monitoring the EoE disease in patients before and after treatment and to differentiate EoE disease from GERD in patients. EoE disease in patients before and after treatment and to differentiate EoE disease from GERD in patients.

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